

PACIFICUS

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- Poetry
- Short Stories
- Essays
- Spotlight on Emerging Writers
- Creative Corner
- Others

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“WHEN GOD HEARS”

When God listens to our gentle whispers in the night,
He covers our biggest fears in morning light.
Every falling tear, every ignored plea,
God embraces us with love and mystery.

When God hears our hearts too weary to speak,
He raises the low, uplift the weak.
No cry too small, no sigh hidden.
God’s grace pours gently in between.

When God hears our prayers we cannot utter,
He answers calm, in His own way.
With powerful strength, He calms our years.
Peace begins... when our faithful God hears.